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New geological insights and structural control on fluid circulation in La Fossa cone (Vulcano, Aeolian Islands, Italy)

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1 **New geological insights and structural control on fluid circulation**
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32 **Abstract**

33

34 Electric resistivity tomography (ERT), self-potential (SP), soil CO₂ flux, and
35 temperature are used to study the inner structure of La Fossa cone (Vulcano, Aeolian Islands).
36 Nine profiles were performed across the cone with a measurement spacing of 20 m. The crater
37 rims of La Fossa cone are underlined by sharp horizontal resistivity contrasts. SP, CO₂ flux,
38 and temperature anomalies underline these boundaries which we interpret as structural limits
39 associated to preferential circulation of fluids. The Pietre Cotte crater and Gran Cratere craters
40 enclose the main hydrothermal system, identified at the centre of the edifice on the base of
41 low electrical resistivity values ($< 20 \Omega.m$) and strong CO₂ degassing, SP, and temperature
42 anomalies. In the periphery, the hydrothermal activity is also visible along structural
43 boundaries such as the Punte Nere, Forgia Vecchia, and Palizzi crater rims and at the base of
44 the cone, on the southern side of the edifice, along a fault attributed to the NW main tectonic
45 trend of the island. Inside the Punte Nere crater, the ERT sections show an electrical resistive
46 body that we interpret as an intrusion or a dome. This magmatic body is reconstructed in 3D
47 using the available ERT profiles. Its shape and position, with respect to the Pietre Cotte crater
48 fault, allows replacing this structure in the chronology of the development of the volcano. It
49 corresponds to a late phase of activity of the Punte Nere edifice. Considering the position of
50 the SP, soil CO₂ flux, and temperature maxima and the repartition of conductive zones related
51 to hydrothermal circulation with respect to the main structural features, La Fossa cone could
52 be considered as a relevant example of the strong influence of pre-existing structures on
53 hydrothermal fluid circulation at the scale of a volcanic edifice.

54

55

56 **Keywords:** Electrical resistivity; self-potential; soil CO₂ degassing; temperature; fluid
57 circulation; hydrothermal system; structural boundary; Vulcano; La Fossa cone.

58

59 **Short title:** Structural control on fluid circulation

60

61

62 1. Introduction

63

64 Active volcanoes are not only the place of magma transfers but also of permanent heat
65 and fluid transfers from the magma reservoir to the surface, even during long periods of
66 eruptive quiescence. These exchanges are mainly insured by convective circulations of hot
67 ground fluids (gas and liquids) inside the hydrothermal system (e.g., Aubert and Baubron,
68 1988; Granieri et al., 2006; Finizola et al., 2003, 2006).

69 A volcanic edifice can be a very heterogeneous structure due to its eruptive dynamics
70 and evolution. It is usually shaped by an alternation of lava flow units, ash layers,
71 volcanoclastic deposits, clay-rich materials resulting from hydrothermal alteration, various
72 intrusions, all heterogeneously affected by deformation and the presence of cracks. During its
73 evolution, more permeable levels and interfaces develop owing to the superposition of the
74 various geological units. However, structural limits and fracture zones formed inside the
75 volcano along its history can constitute the more permeable zones. These weakness planes
76 allow the infiltration of meteoric waters, the rise of hydrothermal fluids, and sometimes the
77 transfer of magma. A good example is provided by caldera structures, where the hydrothermal
78 activity concentrates along the border fault and on intracalderic fractures (e.g., Pribnow et al.,
79 2003). In a comparative study of the Valles caldera (New Mexico) and of the calderas of Lake
80 City and Platoro (Colorado), Wohletz and Heiken (1992) highlights that the hydrothermal
81 alteration develops principally along the faults formed inside the caldera and around shallow
82 intrusions. Also, the craters boundaries being highly permeable zones of the edifice, they
83 usually guide fluid circulation in the same way (e.g., Revil et al., 2004). In addition to these
84 localized pathways, the transfers can be more pervasive depending on the permeability of the
85 volcanic materials, e.g., the diffuse degassing of CO₂ (Baubron et al., 1990; Allard et al.,
86 1991).

87 The hydrothermal activity can also alter the cohesion of rocks and therefore be
88 responsible for large collapses and landslides or for the spreading of volcanic edifices (Lopez
89 and Williams, 1993; Day, 1996; Vallance and Scott, 1997; Voight and Elsworth, 1997; van
90 Wyk de Vries et al., 2000; Reid et al., 2001; Cecchi et al., 2005; Merle and Lénat, 2003). The
91 hydrothermal alteration, in addition to increasing the risk of instability, also enhances the
92 mobility of the debris avalanches. Indeed, the hydrothermal alteration reduces the cohesion of
93 the rock and increases the fluid content favouring these risks (e.g., Vallance and Scott 1997).
94 On Vulcano, a landslide occurred the 20th April 1988 on the north-eastern flank of La Fossa
95 cone. A volume of 220.000 m³ of superficial pyroclastic deposits was implicated. This

96 destabilization was contemporary of the opening of fractures affected by fumarolic
97 emanations and hydrothermal alteration (Ricci, 2007). Currently, given the strong alteration
98 of the rocks around the Forgia Vecchia (north-north-east flank) this area is of major landslide-
99 probability and, due to the population density, in particular during the tourist season, it
100 presents a major risk. Understanding the relationships between pre-existing structures and
101 fluid circulation is important to study volcanic hydrothermal systems and could help to
102 forecast possible volcanic instabilities in the long term.

103 Because drilling volcanic edifices is difficult, non-intrusive methods that can image
104 the structure of a volcanic edifice and that can be sensitive to the flow of the ground water and
105 CO₂ are important to understand the dynamics of hydrothermal systems. They constitute very
106 important tools to extrapolate the observations made at the ground surface to depth in order to
107 draw a map of the geohazards associated with a volcanic edifice. La Fossa cone (Vulcano,
108 Aeolian Islands, Italy) is a small and complex volcanic edifice characterized by a strong
109 alteration due to a very active hydrothermal system. In addition, we have a good knowledge
110 regarding its eruptive history (De Astis et al., 2007 and references therein). It is therefore an
111 ideal natural laboratory to conduct a high resolution survey investigating the structure and the
112 hydrothermal system of a volcanic edifice.

113 We acquired multi-electrode electric resistivity data (ERT), self potential (SP), soil
114 CO₂ diffuse degassing, and shallow ground temperature data along several profiles. The same
115 dataset was used by Revil et al. (2008) to present the main structural features interpreted from
116 some of the profiles and to perform a numerical modelling of the ground water flow pattern.
117 In our case, this multidisciplinary study is used to map the signature of the hydrothermal
118 activity of La Fossa cone and to detail its inner structure above the sea level.

119 The main goals of this study are (1) to interpret the data in terms of geological features
120 and (2) to understand how pre-existing geological structures control the pattern of fluid
121 circulation.

122

123

124 **2. Geological setting**

125

126 Located in the south of Tyrrhenian Basin, Vulcano is the third largest of the seven
127 Aeolian Islands. It is also the southernmost island of the archipelago. Salina, Lipari, and
128 Vulcano are three islands aligned along a NNW-SSE trend, unconformable with respect to the
129 arc layout. This volcanic lineament is explained by a magmatic activity controlled by regional

130 tectonics. Indeed, the development of these islands is strongly influenced by an active crustal
131 discontinuity related to the Tindari-Letojanni dextral strike-slip fault system formed in the
132 continuation of the Malta escarpment (Barberi et al., 1994; Ventura, 1994; Ghisetti, 1979).
133 The horizontal displacements along the strike-slip system are accommodated by N-S to NE-
134 SW trending normal faults and accompanied by pure extension (Mazzuoli et al., 1995).

135 Vulcano Island was built by a succession of constructive and destructive stages of the
136 two main edifices, Vulcano Primordiale and La Fossa cone (Fig. 1). Vulcano Primordiale is
137 the oldest (120-100 ka, see Keller, 1980). This unit, located in the southern part on the island,
138 is also commonly named Piano or Serro di Punta Lunga. This stratovolcano has been
139 truncated around 100 ka by the collapse of the Piano Caldera, now filled by post-collapse
140 eruptive materials (De Astis et al., 1989). The eruptive centre has then migrated to the north-
141 west to form the Cardo tuff cone and the Lentia intrusive Complex. Both have been largely
142 masked owing to the collapse of La Fossa Caldera and because of the edification of La Fossa
143 cone inside the caldera depression (De Astis et al., 2007).

144 La Fossa cone is a 391 m height stratocone, active since ~6000 years (Dellino and La
145 Volpe, 1997; De Rosa et al., 2004). Its eruptive history and structure have been studied by
146 many authors (e.g., Keller, 1970, 1980; Frazzetta et al., 1983, 1984; Dellino and La Volpe
147 1997; De Astis et al., 1997, 2003, Arrighi et al., 2006). The present day edifice results from
148 six main phases of activity described in the last issue of the geological map of the island (De
149 Astis et al., 2007) which we simplified in Figure 1.

150 (1) Punte Nere formation is composed of pyroclastic products corresponding to surges and
151 fallouts deposits at the base. The upper unit is a succession of aa lava flows. This formation
152 constitutes the former Fossa cone, associated to Punte Nere crater (PN) and now truncated to
153 the west by the younger cone.

154 (2) Palizzi formation is composed of three units. The first unit show a pyroclastic succession
155 of varicoloured ashes (“Tufi varicolori di La Fossa”). Two younger units display an
156 alternation of pyroclastic deposits and lava flows. In the meantime, a new eruptive centre was
157 active in the northern part of the island, forming the Vulcanello peninsula. The corresponding
158 crater rim (Pa) is nowadays only visible on the southern part of La Fossa cone.

159 (3) Caruggi formation, previously named Commenda (Frazzetta et al., 1984; Arrighi et al.,
160 2006) consists of pyroclastic deposits with yellow-reddish ashes and rounded,
161 hydrothermalized lithic blocks. The upper unit corresponds to varicoloured tuffs and ash
162 layers. This layer is well recognized in the landscape as pink coloured outcrops.

163 (4) Forgia Vecchia formation has settled on the northern flank of La Fossa cone and is made
164 up of lahar deposits. This stage also left an adventive crater (FV), approximately 300 m wide,
165 on the northern flank.

166 (5) Pietre Cotte formation consists of a pyroclastic unit mainly visible on the southern flank of
167 La Fossa cone. The cycle is ended by the emission of a striking tongue-like rhyolitic lava flow
168 easily recognisable on the northwest flank. The corresponding crater of Pietre Cotte stage
169 (PC) intersects both PN and Pa craters.

170 (6) Gran Cratere formation is a pyroclastic level clearly visible on the major part of La Fossa
171 cone as grey ashes. This stage of activity ended with the historical 1888-1890 eruption and
172 gave rise to the formation of a succession of nested craters (GC) partly overlapping the PC
173 crater rim.

174 The current activity on Vulcano is characterized by intense fumarolic emissions in La
175 Fossa crater, on the northern and southern flanks of the edifice and in the area of the Porto di
176 Levante harbour. Other isolated fumaroles have been observed on the flanks of the edifice
177 while a strong cold degassing is localized in the Palizzi area. Since 1890 the quiescent La
178 Fossa volcano is characterized by the occurrence of “crises” (Granieri et al., 2006) with strong
179 increases of the fumaroles temperatures and output and variations of the chemical
180 compositions toward more magmatic signatures caused by the uprising of magmatic gas.
181 Moreover, a local anomalous shallow seismicity characterized by swarms of low-magnitude,
182 due to rising gases in the fumarolic feeding system, an increase of the diffuse soil CO₂
183 degassing, and a spatial expansion of the fumarolic fields are also characteristic of these
184 “crises” but no evidence of magma uprising was signaled.

185

186 **3. Data acquisition and processing**

187

188 In October 2005, May 2006 and October 2006 we performed three multidisciplinary
189 surveys. Nine profiles were deployed crossing the entire edifice, for a total length of 18980 m
190 (Fig. 2). We acquired multi-electrode electrical resistivity data with an electrode spacing of
191 20 m. Self potential, CO₂, and temperature measurements were acquired on the same points,
192 which represent 957 measurements for these methods. The methods used during the surveys
193 are described in detail in Revil et al. (2008). We summarize the main points here:

194

195 **3.1. Electric resistivity tomography**

196

197 Resistivity measurements were acquired with an ABEM (SAS4000) resistivimeter
198 with a multichannel system of 64 electrodes connected to the acquisition system through a
199 1260 m long cable. We used a Wenner array because of its good signal-to-noise ratio. We
200 added salty water around each electrode to decrease the contact resistance between the
201 electrodes and the ground. Two or three roll-along were performed to complete each profile.
202 The apparent resistivity values obtained were inverted by RES2DINV software (Geotomo
203 software; Griffiths and Barker, 1993; Loke and Barker, 1996) obtaining a resistivity model
204 along each section. Revil et al. (2008) detailed the inversion process and discussed the results
205 of the tests run to check the uncertainty associated with the resistivity data. The authors
206 conclude that the inverse modelling used is very robust to the noise existing in the raw data.
207 The results allow visualizing a model of resistivity of the edifice. Some of the most
208 representative resistivity models will be presented below as 2D cross-sections.

209 The interpretation of inverted data alone is a notoriously difficult task because
210 electrical resistivity varies with a number of parameters including temperature, salinity, clay
211 and zeolite contents and mineralogy, grain shape, and porosity (Revil et al., 2002; Rabaute et
212 al., 2003). For the same data set, there are several possible resistivity models that fit the data
213 equally well (e.g., Auken and Christiansen, 2004; Binley and Kemna, 2005). However, the
214 resistivity models highlight clear spatial resistivity contrasts that can be interpreted in terms of
215 lithology transitions.

216

217 **3.2. Self potential**

218

219 SP measurements were performed using a pair of non-polarizing Cu/CuSO_4
220 electrodes. The difference of electrical potential between the reference electrode
221 (conventionally placed at the beginning of the profile) and the scanning electrode was
222 measured with a calibrated high impedance voltmeter with a sensitivity of 0.1 mV. The SP
223 method allows to map rising hydrothermal fluids on active volcanoes; e.g., on Kilauea in
224 Hawaii (Zablocki, 1976), on Nevado de Colima and Fuego de Colima in Mexico (Aubert and
225 Lima, 1986), on Piton de la Fournaise in Reunion Island (Malengreau et al., 1994 and Michel
226 and Zlotnicki, 1998), on the Karthala in Comoros (Durand, 1997; Lénat et al., 1998), on
227 Stromboli in Italy (Finizola et al., 2002), and on Misti volcano in Peru (Finizola et al., 2004).
228 In the present case, this method was useful to highlight the structural limits, which are usually
229 preferential paths for ground water circulation and to map the hydrothermal activity.

230

231 3.3. Soil CO₂ flux

232

233 Soil CO₂ flux measurements were acquired using the methodology described by
234 Chiodini et al. (1998). The instrumentation consists of an IR spectrometer Licor LI800 with a
235 range of 0 to 2000 µmol/mol (2 % vol.), an accumulation chamber (type A: volume of
236 30 cm³) and a palmtop to plot the CO₂ increase as a function of time. The accumulation
237 chamber is leaned on the ground so that the atmospheric air cannot penetrate inside. The gas
238 permeating from the soil accumulates in the dead volume, passes through the IR spectrometer
239 and is re-injected in the accumulation chamber. The increase of the concentration in the
240 chamber through time allows determining the flux of CO₂ from the soil. This is a powerful
241 method to detect preferential hydrothermal flux paths on a volcanic edifice.

242

243 3.4. Temperature at 30 cm depth

244

245 Temperature measurements were performed at a depth of 30 cm ± 1 cm and
246 respecting a stabilisation time of 15 minutes. We used thermal probes and a digital
247 thermometer with a sensitivity of 0.1°C. The maximum amplitude of diurnal variation at
248 Vulcano at 30 cm depth during the summer season is less than 1.2°C (Chébli, 1997; Aubert et
249 al., 2007). During the year, at that depth, the temperature varies from 12.2 to 27.2°C in
250 January and August, respectively (Lo Cascio and Navarra, 1997). Consequently, for
251 measurements performed at 30 cm depth, we consider a temperature above 30°C as a
252 signature of hydrothermal fluid circulations.

253 We made a temperature map interpolated from the data of the nine profiles (Fig. 3a).
254 The data have been acquired within one year so that the amplitude of the thermal anomalies
255 probably varied along the period of acquisition of the dataset due to seasonal and internal
256 variations. However this figure gives reliable qualitative information.

257

258 4. Results

259

260 4.1. Reliability of the temperature, CO₂, and SP maps

261

262 A map is supposed to present the state of a particular area within a short period of
263 time, which suggests that the conditions along the acquisition of a dataset must remain
264 relatively stable. Our dataset contains data from three surveys performed in a one year period

265 (from October 2005 to October 2006). Concerning the SP measurements, we added a few data
266 from a survey of 2004 (black dots on Figure 3b) in order to join the profiles to the sea,
267 calculate a closure offset and distribute linearly this offset on the profiles to correct the global
268 dataset presented here. Knowing that, we must take into account that some parameters
269 influencing the measurements have undergone some variations, which can distort the maps.
270 These parameters are the volcanic activity, the soil characteristics and the atmospheric
271 conditions.

272 It seems that the temperature measurements at 30 cm depth are less affected by the
273 variations undergone between our three surveys. It is true since the measurements are not
274 performed during rain events. In fact the rain makes the temperature fall down of several
275 degrees depending on the depth of infiltration of the meteoric water and the atmospheric
276 temperature.

277 For the SP map, some strong positive and negative anomalies remain uncorrelated
278 with the other methods and the main information is displayed in the PC/GC crater area and
279 the PN crater. Variations of the volcanic activity, seasonal variations of the soil moisture are
280 the possible responsible of some of the unexplained anomalies. The contrasts of resistivity of
281 the terrain can also affect the SP measurements without affecting the CO₂ and temperature
282 values.

283 The values of the soil diffuse degassing at La Fossa volcano during the last crisis,
284 begun at the end of 2004, revealed fluctuations of CO₂ flux until one order of magnitude
285 (Granieri et al., 2006). It was characterized by significant variations in the extension of the
286 anomalous degassing area. The CO₂ flux data presented in this paper were collected in three
287 different periods during the last crisis of La Fossa volcano. Consequently, the resulting CO₂
288 map of the entire La Fossa cone shown in Figure 3c is purely indicative because of the
289 fluctuations in the degassing activity and no quantitative analyses can be done. Nevertheless
290 the CO₂ map closely reflects the shape of the anomalous degassing areas presented by
291 Granieri et al. (2006).

292 Finally, more than giving quantitative information, the temperature, SP, and CO₂ maps
293 are useful to get qualitative information, i.e. structural information and a distribution of the
294 hydrothermal emissions. Based on the correlations between these maps, several areas of
295 interest have been identified and will be commented below.

296

297 **4.2. The central hydrothermal system**

298

299 In an interpolated map, the less the profiles are spaced, the more the interpolation is
300 reliable so that, on the temperature, SP, and CO₂ maps, the most relevant information is
301 concentrated around the data points (white and black dots on Figure 3). The most striking
302 information provided by the global temperature map (Figure 3a) is that the main thermal
303 anomaly is bounded by the rim of the GC and PC craters, which are the most recent craters
304 formed on La Fossa cone. This central thermal anomaly is correlated to anomalies of similar
305 extension in SP and soil CO₂ flux (maps in Figure 3b and 3c).

306 The highest temperatures have been measured into the inner crater. Gases escape from
307 the fumaroles at high temperature (~400°C) and, for the safety of the measuring devices, no
308 measurement was made right on it. In the north-east area, the thermal, SP and CO₂ anomalies
309 extend beyond the GC rim, between the GC and the PC crater rims. In the field, these zones
310 correspond to strong fumarolic activity and/or extensive hydrothermal alteration. The main
311 fumarolic field is indeed located on the northern wall of the GC crater, on the rim, and
312 extends beyond its limits (see Bukumirovic et al., 1997). On Vulcano, the temperatures of the
313 fumaroles can reach several hundred degrees Celsius (almost 700°C during the 1977 crisis,
314 see Barberi et al., 1991). Except on these particular locations, no measurement of our surveys
315 overtakes 98°C. This can be explained by the presence, at depth, of a hot aquifer or of a
316 shallow condensation zone formed under a sealed layer, acting as a thermal buffer between
317 the magmatic heat source and the surface (Montalto 1994; Aubert et al., 2007).

318 These main thermal, SP, and CO₂ anomalies are the expression of the central active
319 hydrothermal system activity and the data show that this hydrothermal system is bounded by
320 the PC and GC crater faults.

321

322 **4.3. Hydrothermal circulations along former structural limits**

323

324 Hydrothermal fluid circulation is not restricted to the central crater area. Outside of the
325 main Fossa craters area, we also identified few temperature, SP, and CO₂ anomalies. Not far
326 from the central hydrothermal system, strong anomalies have been observed beyond the PC
327 crater rim, on the northwest upper flank of the cone, right on the former footpath to the
328 summit (see the central part of profile 2 in Figure 3). These high temperatures, SP, and CO₂
329 values are associated with fumarolic emissions.

330

331 **4.3.1 Forgia Vecchia crater**

332

333 On the northern flank, the Forgia Vecchia crater (FV) is affected by a thermal anomaly
334 on its northern border (see northern section of Profile 3 on Figure 3a). The temperature
335 measured is $\sim 10^{\circ}\text{C}$ above the mean temperature in this area. This is the only sign of current
336 activity on this adventive crater, in our dataset. The FV crater border is a permeable limit
337 acting as a guide for fluid circulation. The thermal release noticed here can be due to the
338 presence, at shallow depth, of a still cooling magmatic batch related to the past activity.
339 Another source could be distal hot fluid circulations associated to the current hydrothermal
340 system of La Fossa cone.

341

342 **4.3.2 Palizzi crater**

343

344 On the southern flank of the edifice, Profiles 3, 5, and 6 display thermal and CO_2
345 anomalies on their intersection with the Pa crater rim. This crater rim is clearly underlined,
346 even when the topography gives no evidence for it. The location of the anomalies coincides
347 with the crater drawn by De Astis et al. (2007) in their geological map of Vulcano.

348

349 **4.3.3 Punte Nere crater**

350

351 One striking result is the observation of high temperature, SP, and CO_2 values in the
352 area enclosed by the Punte Nere crater (PN), where no eruptive activity took place since
353 3.8 ka (De Astis et al., 2007). As shown by the data along the two profiles crossing the rim in
354 the North (Profile 6) and in the East (Profile 8), the thermal and CO_2 anomalies extend
355 outside the PN crater, on the upper part of the slope of the cone.

356 Two types of thermal anomalies can be distinguished in this area, which are (1) strong
357 anomalies (in the range between 35°C and 60°C) along structural limits and (2) weak
358 anomalies (smaller than 35°C) in areas poorly or unaffected by faulting. On Profiles 6 and 8,
359 the temperature anomalies show that hydrothermal fluids take advantage of the high
360 permeability along the crater rim to reach the ground surface. The maximum temperature
361 registered is $\sim 60^{\circ}\text{C}$. In this case, the heat can come from a deep source and produce strong
362 anomalies in the vicinity of the ground surface. Concerning the wide anomalous temperature
363 field inside the PN crater, temperatures reach a maximum of 35°C .

364 As for the FV crater but to a wider scale, the PN crater anomaly can have two potential
365 origins: the hot-fluid source can be due either to circulations of fluids from La Fossa
366 hydrothermal system or to remnants of the past activity of the Punte Nere cone. Profile 1 can

367 help determining the source (Fig. 4). As on the maps (Fig. 3), an overview of this
368 profile shows high values of temperature, self-potential, and CO₂ in the central part of the
369 edifice. The self-potential data display a typical W shape (e.g., Ishido, 2004), confirming that
370 the main hydrothermal activity is concentrated in the limits of the GC crater. Crossing the
371 eastern side of the GC crater rim, the temperature and CO₂ progressively decrease from west
372 to east, inside the PN crater. The anomaly vanishes to reach characteristic temperatures of
373 “cold” zones on the flank of the edifice. At depth, the resistivity structure shows a continuous
374 conductive zone from the most internal crater to the flank of the cone. In the limits of the PC
375 crater, the low resistivity is associated to the hydrothermal system, i.e. hydrothermal fluids
376 convecting through the detritic volcanic deposits of the last phases of eruptive activity.
377 Beyond the PC crater, we interpret the low resistivity layer as tuff deposits from La Fossa
378 activity. The resistive body visible at depth acts as an impermeable limit so that the fluids are
379 guided inside the more permeable overlying tuff level. Underground, the hot fluids rising
380 from the central zone overflow to the east into the PN crater and progressively loose gases
381 and heat. The temperature, SP, and CO₂ anomalies visible inside the PN crater can be
382 attributed to this phenomenon, even if a contribution of a residual degassing activity of the PN
383 volcanic centre cannot be ruled out.

384

385 **4.4. Regional faulting evidences in the Palizzi area**

386

387 Profile 4 was performed at the base of the cone, from Porto di Levante to an area
388 situated to the East of Palizzi, near the Rio Grande bed. The CO₂ map (Fig. 3c) shows
389 remarkable anomalies in the Palizzi area. The global temperature map (Fig. 3a) does not
390 display a perceptible anomaly along Profile 4. However, a closer inspection of the data
391 indicates a variation of ~6°C from one extremity of the profile to the other (see Figures 5 and
392 6). At the south-eastern end of the profile, the temperature is ~18°C. Following the profile to
393 Porto di Levante, the temperature increases progressively and reaches a maximum of ~24°C.
394 The data were acquired in only two days and with similar dry meteorological conditions all
395 along this period of time. Moreover, this progressive temperature increase of ~6°C from the
396 southern flank to the north-western flank of La Fossa cone exceeds the maximum amplitude
397 of diurnal variation which is less than 1.2°C at Vulcano, for measurements performed at
398 30 cm depth during summer season (Chébli, 1997; Aubert et al., 2007). This makes of these
399 6°C a significant variation.

400 In the northern and southern parts of the profile, the ERT model shows a shallow
401 resistive layer associated to pyroclastic deposits. These deposits are from the Gran Cratere
402 phase of activity in the northern portion of the profile and from the Palizzi phase in the south.
403 This resistive layer of a few meters-thick overlays a low-resistivity medium ($< 20 \Omega.m$). At
404 the center of the profile, we notice the presence of a high resistivity zone. The thickness of
405 this body globally increases from north to south. This structure is bounded by two vertical
406 limits evidenced by sharp transitions of the resistivity. The northern boundary is rapidly
407 blurring at depth. The southern boundary is marked by a sharpest transition of resistivity and
408 runs from the shallow levels of the section, until the maximum depth of investigation.

409 On the northern part of the profile, the soil CO_2 flux decreases from north to south
410 consistently with the global decrease of temperature observed along the whole profile. In the
411 vicinity of the resistive body, the CO_2 flux increases, reaching a maximum in the area
412 surrounding the southern vertical limit identified from the resistivity data. On the area
413 surrounding the resistive body the short wave-length variations of the temperature are
414 significantly lower than on the rest of the profile. Thereby, along our profile, the southern
415 vertical limit of the resistive body marks a sharp increase of $\sim 2.5^\circ C$ of the mean temperature
416 from north to south. Right on the northern boundary of the body, we also observe a slight soil
417 CO_2 flux anomaly ($\sim 80 g/m^2.d$) and a decrease of the SP signal ($\sim 50 mV$).

418 Capasso et al. (2000) analysed partial pressures of He and CO_2 of some water samples
419 from the north-eastern quarter of La Fossa cone area. They observed that the values of these
420 partial pressures were appreciably higher than those in waters in equilibrium with the
421 atmosphere, therefore showing interaction between volcanic gases and groundwater. Our data
422 are consistent with those results and we interpret the gradient observed along Profile 4 as the
423 evidence of preferential hot fluid circulations at the base of the north-western flank of La
424 Fossa cone. The peaks of CO_2 flux in our data, around Palizzi are consistent with soil gas
425 samples analysed by Capasso et al. (1997) in the same zone. The authors measured
426 widespread exhalative manifestations dominated by CO_2 on Palizzi that they interpreted in
427 terms of hydrothermal circulation. The local anomalies we observed and the associated
428 vertical limit pointed out by the ERT data lead us to interpret this signal as hydrothermal fluid
429 circulation rising along a volcano-tectonic structure. This structure could be related to the
430 NNW Tindari-Letojanni regional fault system, identified in the southern sector of La Fossa
431 caldera (Barberi et al., 1994). The northern boundary of the resistive body is not deeply rooted
432 as is the southern one. This limit is likely only a lithological transition. The resistive rocks,
433 probably a lava flow pile or a lava dome, constitute an impermeable limit to fluid circulation.

434 The anomalies registered here are likely due to circulation of fluids guided along the
435 lithological boundary.

436

437 **4.5. Comparison between the data and the geology**

438

439 **4.5.1. Signals associated to the various volcanic formations**

440

441 The ERT data allow visualizing almost the entire cone above sea level. The profiles
442 detailed in the following paragraphs cross the main structures identified on the volcanic
443 edifice. In the first layers of the sections, the ERT data can be easily correlated to field
444 observations. Indeed, in all the profiles, the Gran Cratere grey ash formation appears as a
445 high-resistivity layer (see Figures 4, 5, 7, 8). At the base of this resistive layer, the sharp
446 transition in electrical resistivity can be interpreted as a sharp lithological transition. Thereby
447 this interface can be followed at depth, along the slopes of the cone. The ERT sections display
448 a thickness of ~20-30 m which could be attributed to the presence of the Gran Cratere, the
449 Pietre Cotte and, the Forgia Vecchia formations.

450 The tuff outcrops, mostly corresponding to the Palizzi and Caruggi pyroclastic
451 formations, are correlated to low resistivity values ($< 20 \Omega.m$). This is visible in various
452 outcrops as in the northern part of profile 6 (Fig. 7). These low resistivity values result from
453 the cation exchange capacity of clay minerals and zeolites composing the Vulcano tuff and
454 are indicative of the alteration of the rock (see Roberts and Lin, 1997; Revil et al., 2002;
455 Bernard et al., 2007).

456 Also in the southern part of Profile 8, the GC crater cliff shows the succession of an
457 upper electrical resistive layer overlying a conductive layer (Fig. 8). In the field they are
458 related respectively to (1) the Gran Cratere ash and Pietre Cotte deposits and (2) to the
459 Caruggi tuff deposits (see the simplified geologic map of Figure 1).

460

461 **4.5.2. Signals associated to the fumaroles**

462

463 In the field, the fumaroles are concentrated along the most recent crater rims. The
464 fumarolic fields inside the GC crater coincide with very low resistivity values, in the same
465 order of magnitude than the tuffs deposits. The difference between “cold” tuffs and rocks
466 affected by hydrothermal convection is highlighted by field observations, self-potential,
467 temperature, and CO₂ flux measurements. Profile 6 shows highly conductive terrains

468 (< 20 Ω .m) right under the most active fumaroles of La Fossa cone (Fig. 7). These conductive
469 values are correlated with a temperature anomaly reaching 95°C, a positive self-potential
470 anomaly of 100 mV (variation with respect to the mean SP value in this zone) and a CO₂ flux
471 peak reaching ~10,000 g/m².d in the vicinity of the fumaroles. The most striking feature is the
472 resistivity model showing a conductive channel running from the fumaroles at the surface, to
473 the central hydrothermal system, until the maximum depth of investigation. The channel is
474 progressively widening with depth. It developed thanks to a pre-existent structural limit,
475 which is the GC crater.

476

477 **4.5.3. Signals associated to crater boundaries**

478

479 The craters identified through the morphology of the edifice and from a previous work
480 (De Astis et al., 2007) are correlated with sharp horizontal transitions of resistivity forming
481 more or less vertical limits. The best example is given by the south-west border of the GC
482 crater which is crossed by profiles 1 and 8 (figures 4 and 8). It displays a vertical to slightly
483 reverse-slope border delimiting high resistivities (> 150 Ω .m) outside the crater and low
484 resistivities (< 20 Ω .m) inside the crater. As seen before, at the surface, a clear anomaly in
485 temperature, self-potential, and CO₂ flux, spots this boundary, at the base of the crater cliff.
486 This type of configuration, related to a structural limit, can be observed for most of the crater
487 rims identified.

488

489 The reverse dip of the crater border faults is a common consequence of caldera-type or
490 pit-crater-type collapse of a crater roof (e.g. Anderson, 1936; Branney, 1995; Acocella et al.,
491 2000; Roche et al., 2000 and 2001; Walter and Troll, 2001). Therefore, GC crater could have
492 been affected by this type of collapse during its formation. A similar dipping is not observed
493 on the north-eastern border maybe because the collapse was asymmetric. Hydrothermal
494 circulations and alteration in the vicinity of the eastern magma body evidenced under the PN
495 crater could also have modified the resistivity distribution appearing nowadays and distort the
496 observation on this side (Cf. next section: 4.6. The Eastern electrical resistive body).

496

497 **4.6. The eastern electrical resistive body**

498

499 On all the sections crossing the eastern half of the edifice, a wide resistive body has
500 been highlighted inside the PN crater, buried under younger formations. Profiles 1, 5, 6, 7, 8,
501 and 9 (see Figure 2 for position of the profiles) clearly show a zone of resistivities ranging

502 from 200 Ω .m to 1000 Ω .m, at depth. These high resistivity zones are in the range of the
503 values expected for a lava flow pile or intrusive rocks (a dyke system, a shallow magma batch
504 or a dome; e.g., see Figure 1.5 of Loke, 2004). The resistivity of the terrain depends mainly
505 on the interconnected porosity of the rock and on the resistivity of the pore fluids. As an
506 example, in a dome, a significant proportion of the vesicles are isolated and refilled by
507 volcanic gas (e.g., see Ramsey and Fink, 1999) which confers a high resistivity to the rock.

508 It is important to notice that the inversion of ERT data tends to smooth the resistivity
509 transitions i.e. the interfaces between the different geologic units. The boundary of the
510 electrical resistive body is delimited by a sharp variation of the resistivity values, which can
511 be associated to a lithological transition. On the resistivity models, the sharper transition is
512 observed for an average value of ~ 160 Ω .m. Based on this assessment, the minimum depth of
513 the resistive body can be estimated to ~ 50 m. This suggests that this unit is buried under
514 additional formations than just the Gran Cratere pyroclastic deposits.

515 The density of the inverted resistivity data allowed us to reconstruct the shape of this
516 resistive body buried inside the Punte Nere crater. To this purpose, the six ERT profiles cited
517 above have been used. On each profile, the 160 Ω .m iso-resistivity line has been digitized with
518 one point every 20 m (in the horizontal plane). The XYZ coordinates obtained were
519 interpolated and represented as a surface map (Fig. 9).

520 The lateral and vertical maximum extension of the body is not accessible as it extends
521 under the depth of investigation. It displays a crescent shape with an irregular surface. The
522 eastern side is a more or less regular slope, slightly steeper than the topographic surface
523 while, to the West, the resistive body ends with a vertical boundary. This straight western
524 limit coincides nicely with the PC crater rim.

525 Blanco-Montenegro et al. (2007) found a magnetic anomaly inside the PN crater. The
526 authors interpreted this anomaly as a pile of tephritic lavas emplaced in an early phase of
527 activity of La Fossa cone. From our ERT data, the shape, position and range of resistivity of
528 this body led us to interpret it as an intrusion or a dome contemporary of the activity of the
529 PN cone (5.3 ka – 3.8 ka) and truncated to the west, on at least 200 m depth by the PC crater
530 ring fault during its formation (1739 A.D.) (See Figure 10). The presence of this large buried
531 magma body, if it is not totally cooled down and degassed, can contribute to the thermal and
532 CO₂ flux anomalies observed inside the PN crater (Fig. 8).

533

534 **5. Conclusions**

535

536 All the geophysical and geochemical anomalies we evidenced at the surface of La
537 Fossa cone are controlled by structural limits. The main hydrothermal system is enclosed by
538 the boundaries of the PC and GC craters. This is indicated by the low resistivity value of the
539 formations and by the strong self-potential, CO₂ flux, and temperature anomalies measured in
540 the limits of these craters. The hydrothermal activity is not restricted to the central part of the
541 edifice. In the periphery, hydrothermal circulations have been evidenced and are, most of the
542 time, clearly influenced by the structure of the edifice. This structure corresponds either to
543 lithological levels or to structural limits and the following conclusions have been reached:

544 (1) The hydrothermal fluids rising from the central hydrothermal system of the GC
545 crater condensate at shallow depth and partly flow down to the PN crater, through the more
546 permeable levels. They are guided along the PC crater border and the resistive body
547 highlighted at depth by electrical resistivity tomography.

548 (2) The Palizzi area is affected by circulations of hydrothermal fluids associated to the
549 presence of a vertical structural limit visible in the resistivity tomography at the base of the
550 edifice. This fault reaching more than 100 m b.s.l. could be attributed to the NNW regional
551 volcano-tectonic orientation affecting the island of Vulcano.

552 (3) The former-crater rims, even when partially buried, remain preferential paths for
553 hydrothermal fluid circulations as evidenced for the FV, PN, and Pa craters, which are
554 underlined by strong temperature and CO₂ degassing anomalies and associated with low
555 resistivity values at depth.

556 Circulations of hydrothermal fluids have been evidenced at the base of the north-
557 western flank, by a variation of temperature of ~6°C from the south-east to the north-west
558 along the profile 4. Such a distal anomaly of temperature can be due either to rising
559 hydrothermal fluids or to fluids contaminated by the hydrothermal release in the summit area
560 and flowing down to the base into shallow ground levels of the north-western flank. The
561 north-western end of Profile 4 could be a relevant site for monitoring the temperature
562 variations, if the fluctuations of the main hydrothermal system activity influence also the
563 hydrothermal circulations at the base of the cone.

564 Our study also reveals the presence of an old magmatic body, dome or shallow
565 intrusion, associated to the activity of the Punte Nere cone. The PC crater intersects this
566 magma body on 200 m high, destructing its western part during the formation of the crater.
567 The interface between the resistive body and the deposits filling the inner crater is one of the
568 major structural limits of the edifice and constitute the eastern limit of the main hydrothermal
569 system of La Fossa cone.

570

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772 **Figure captions:**

773

774 Figure 1. Location of the studied area. Simplified geological map of La Fossa cone draped on
775 the DEM (map simplified from de Astis et al., 2007) and chronology. PN (Punte Nere), Pa
776 (Palizzi), FV (Forgia Vecchia), PC (Pietre Cotte), and GC (Gran Cratere) crater rims are
777 represented. In the upper right corner, Vu, VP, and LFc stand for Vulcanello, Vulcano
778 Primordiale and La Fossa cone. On the location and structural sketch map of the Aeolian
779 Islands area M, AI, TL, and ME stand for the Marsili Oceanic Basin, the Aeolian Islands
780 represented by white ellipses (red star for Vulcano; black shapes for seamounts), the Tindari-
781 Letojanni fault system, and the Malta Escarpment fault system (sketch simplified from
782 Ventura et al., 1999).

783

784 Figure 2. Location of the 9 profiles performed, on the orthophotography overlaid on the DEM
785 of La Fossa cone. Bright orange profiles are those detailed in the text. White dots represent
786 the measure points. The light pink areas on the flanks of the volcano correspond to the
787 hydromagmatic tuff discussed in the main text.

788

789 Figure 3. Temperature, Self potential, and soil CO₂ flux maps of La Fossa cone, interpolated
790 from the data of the nine profiles performed, overlaid on the DEM. White and black dots
791 represent the measure points. PN (Punte Nere), Pa (Palizzi), FV (Forgia Vecchia), PC (Pietre
792 Cotte), and GC (Gran Cratere) craters are localised with white dashed lines.

793

794 Figure 4. Temperature, self-potential, soil CO₂ flux, and electric resistivity tomography along
795 Profile 1. Note the sharp resistivity transition on the GC crater boundaries. PN: Punte Nere
796 crater, PC: Pietre Cotte crater, GC: Gran Cratere crater.

797

798 Figure 5. Temperature, self-potential, soil CO₂ flux, and electric resistivity tomography along
799 profile 4. Note the sharp resistivity transition (black arrow) at a distance of 2000 m underlined
800 by a temperature and soil CO₂ flux maximum. The black arrow is also localized on map in
801 Figure 6.

802

803 Figure 6. Map representation of the temperature variation at the base of the cone, along profile
804 4. White dots represent the measure points. The black arrow is pointing the resistivity
805 transition highlighted by electrical resistivity tomography (see figure 5).

806

807 Figure 7. Temperature, self-potential, soil CO₂ flux, and electric resistivity tomography along
808 profile 6. Note the correspondence of the temperature, self-potential, and soil CO₂ flux
809 anomalies with low values of resistivities reaching the surface. PN: Punte Nere crater, PC:
810 Pietre Cotte crater, GC: Gran Cratere crater, F: fumaroles.

811

812 Figure 8. Temperature, self-potential, soil CO₂ flux, and electric resistivity tomography along
813 profile 8. Note the presence of a large resistive body under the Punte Nere former cone (see
814 also profile 1 on figure 4). PN: Punte Nere crater, PC: Pietre Cotte crater, GC: Gran Cratere
815 crater.

816

817 Figure 9. a. Image map of the electrical resistive body draped on the DEM; b. 3D view of the
818 resistive body under a truncated DEM of La Fossa; c. 3D view of the resistive body from the
819 south-east. The colour scale represents the elevation of the surface of the resistive body. Only
820 the measured points used to build the 3D representation of the resistive body are visible
821 (black and white dots). PN: Punte Nere, Pa: Palizzi, FV: Forgia Vecchia, PC: Pietre Cotte,
822 and GC: Gran Cratere. Coordinates are in meter, UTM (WGS84).

823

824 Figure 10. Schematic representation of the evolution of the cone, from Punte Nere to
825 nowadays. The information on both the geology and on the fluid circulation is shown. The
826 synthetic sketch is based on Profile 8. PN: Punte Nere crater, PC: Pietre Cotte crater, GC:
827 Gran Cratere crater.

828 Figure 1

829

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830 Figure 2

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846 Figure 10

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